

A Longitudinal Survey of Antibiotic-Resistant Enterobacterales in the Irish Environment, 2019–2020

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Antibiotic resistant Enterobacterales were compared from water and sewage sources.
- Genetically identical isolates obtained from sewage sources and surrounding waters.
- One or more carbapenemase producers identified at 23 sampling sites.
- This included *bla*_{OXA-48} (*n* = 18), *bla*_{NDM} (*n* = 14), *bla*_{KPC} (*n* = 4) and *bla*_{OXA-484} (*n* = 1).
- Harmonised monitoring approach needed for environmental resistance surveillance.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

The natural environment represents a complex reservoir of antibiotic-resistant bacteria as a consequence of different wastewater discharges including anthropogenic and agricultural. Therefore, the aim of this study was to examine sewage and waters across Ireland for the presence of antibiotic-resistant Enterobacterales. Samples were collected from the West, East and South of Ireland. Two periods of sampling took place between July 2019 and November 2020, during which 118 water (30 L) and 36 sewage samples (200 mL) were collected. Waters were filtered using the CapE method, followed by enrichment and culturing. Sewage samples were directly cultured on selective agars. Isolates were identified by MALDI-TOF and antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed in accordance with EUCAST criteria. Selected isolates were examined for *bla*_{CTX-M}, *bla*_{VIM}, *bla*_{IMP}, *bla*_{OXA-48}, *bla*_{NDM}, and *bla*_{KPC} by real time PCR and whole genome sequencing (*n* = 146). A total of 419 Enterobacterales (348 water, 71 sewage) were isolated from all samples. Hospital sewage isolates displayed the highest percentage resistance to many beta-lactam and aminoglycoside antibiotics. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producers were identified in 78% of water and 50% of sewage samples. One or more carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales were identified at 23 individual sampling sites (18 water, 5 sewage). This included the detection of *bla*_{OXA-48} (*n* = 18), *bla*_{NDM} (*n* = 14), *bla*_{KPC} (*n* = 4) and *bla*_{OXA-484} (*n* = 1). All NDM-producing isolates harbored the *ble*-*MBL* bleomycin resistance gene. Commonly detected sequence types included *Klebsiella* ST323, ST17, and ST405 as well as *E. coli* ST131, ST38 and ST10. Core genome MLST comparisons detected identical *E. coli* isolates from wastewater treatment plant (WWTP) influent and nursing home sewage, and the surrounding

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waters. Similarly, one *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from WWTP influent and the surrounding estuarine water were identical. These results highlight the need for regular monitoring of the aquatic environment for the presence of antibiotic-resistant organisms to adequately inform public health policies.

Abbreviations

MALDI-TOF

Matrix-Assisted Laser Desorption/Ionization Time of Flight

EUCAST European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing

PCR Polymerase Chain Reaction

WWTP Wastewater treatment plant

WHO World Health Organization

ESBL Extended-Spectrum Beta-Lactamase

CPE Carbapenemase-Producing Enterobacterales

LS1 Longitudinal Survey 1

LS2 Longitudinal Survey 2

MPN Mean Probable Number

CLSI Clinical & Laboratory Standards Institute

ATCC American Type Culture Collection

DNA Deoxyribonucleic Acid

Minlen Minimum length

PE Paired end

MLST Multi Locus Sequence Type

PP Point Prevalence

UWWD Urban Wastewater Discharge

DWTP Drinking water treatment plant

cgMLST Core Genome Multi Locus Sequence Type

ST Sequence Type

DDD Defined Daily Dose

BDU Bed Day Units

PNEC Predicted No-Effect Concentration

ESKAPE *Enterococcus faecium*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, *Acinetobacter baumannii*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa*, and *Enterobacter* species

infections and carriage (European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2019). This report categorised the Republic of Ireland as having inter-regional spread, which is stage 4 on a 5-point scale. A further 11 European countries also reported inter-regional spread including Spain, France and Croatia. A total of four European countries were classed as endemic (stage 5) including Italy, Greece, Turkey, and Malta.

Many reports in relation to antibiotic resistance reference clinical data, but there are large knowledge gaps in relation to the environment as a reservoir and potential transmission route of antibiotic resistance. Therefore, there is an increasing need to apply a One Health approach to the problem of antibiotic resistance. The One Health approach recognises the nexus between humans, animals, and the natural environment (Hernando-Amado et al., 2019). This was highlighted within objective 2 of the WHO's Global Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance, which stated the need for a deeper understanding of how antibiotic resistance circulates 'between humans and animals and through food, water and the environment' (WHO, 2015). This was echoed in Ireland's national action plan published in 2017 (Department of Health, 2017). Under the current EU bathing water monitoring criteria, waters are monitored during the bathing water season for the levels of intestinal enterococci and *E. coli* with no further bacterial characterisation (Directive 2006/7/EC). Therefore, consistent monitoring data relating to environmental antibiotic resistance is lacking, although it has been highlighted as a potential transmission route of multi-drug resistant pathogens to humans via recreational exposure (O'Flaherty et al., 2019; Leonard et al., 2018).

Environmental antibiotic resistance is largely a culmination of the natural resistome, present as a result of antibiotic production by environmental organisms (Hooban et al., 2020), and resistance introduced via wastewater from human and animal sources (He et al., 2020; Pazda et al., 2019). Accordingly, this study was carried out subsequent to the initial point prevalence survey (Hooban et al., 2021) in order to further evaluate the presence of antibiotic-resistant Enterobacterales circulating in sewage and aquatic environments in Ireland. Water bodies receiving multiple anthropogenic discharges as well as those free from them were included for comparison. The results of this study were evaluated against previous findings to examine the effects of seasonality on the presence of resistant organisms. The nexus between anthropogenic wastewater and the natural aquatic environment was established by comparing isolates obtained from both at a genetic level.

1. Introduction

Antibiotics are essential in the treatment of a range of infections responsible for morbidity and mortality in humans and animals. The introduction of more potent and structurally advanced antibiotics in to clinical practice is continuously met with the evolution of new mechanisms of antibiotic resistance (Ventola, 2015). This continuous cycle makes it difficult to ensure successful treatment options are available in cases of multi-drug resistant infections. Mechanisms of antibiotic resistance vary widely from bacterial structural antibiotic target alterations, to the production of enzymes that directly cleave the antibiotic prior to bacterial cell entry (Reygaert, 2018). Often a culmination of mechanisms reduces bacterial susceptibility to a range of antibiotics. A significant factor that increases the difficulty in containing the spread of antibiotic resistance is the ability of bacteria to disseminate mobile genetic elements (e.g. plasmids), often harboring a multitude of resistance genes (Partridge et al., 2018).

Different bacterial species and resistance to distinct antibiotic classes have varying priority rankings. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), Enterobacteriaceae that are carbapenem resistant or extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing (ESBL) are of critical priority for the development of new and effective antibiotics (WHO, 2017). These ranked above vancomycin-resistant *Enterococcus faecium* as well as methicillin and vancomycin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*. On a European scale, an assessment was carried out on data from 2018 evaluating the incidence and distribution of carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae (CPE), inclusive of

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Sample collection sites

Two periods of sample collection were carried out across four local authority areas including Galway City, Galway County, Fingal and Cork County Council as previously described by Hooban et al. (2021). The first sampling period, known as longitudinal survey 1 (LS1), was carried out between August 2019 and January 2020, while the second period (longitudinal survey 2 (LS2)) began in February 2020 and was completed by November 2020. The culmination of both sampling campaigns resulted in the collection and processing of 118 water samples and 36 sewage samples (Supplementary Table 1). Sample collection points were chosen based on the findings of the point prevalence survey (Hooban et al., 2021). A total of 28 water and 7 sewage sampling points were retained across both sampling periods from the initial point prevalence survey. Additional sampling points were added in areas of interest in which carbapenem resistant, ESBL or carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae were previously detected in water bodies. This comprised of an additional 35 water sampling points, which included 27 locations that were sampled twice and 8 areas that were sampled once. The naming designation for these new locations were linked to previous collection sites through the addition of a numerical value following the sample name. For example,

estuary C1 was an additional sample collected in close proximity to estuary C. Water samples included seawaters, lakes, rivers, estuaries, untreated water supplying drinking water treatment plants and an estuarine lagoon. Sewage samples encompassed hospitals, nursing homes, airports and the influent and effluent of wastewater treatment plants.

2.2. Collection and processing of water and sewage samples

A total of 30 L was collected for each water sample. Faecal indicator organisms were quantified using the Colilert-18 (IDEXX) test, for which seawater samples were diluted 1/10 to decrease the salt concentration, prolonging bacterial survival. The processing of water samples was carried out using filtration and enrichment as previously described (Hooban et al., 2021; Morris et al., 2016). Following enrichment, samples were cultured on CHROMagar™ mSuperCARBA™ (CHROMagar), Brilliance™ ESBL agar (Oxoid) and McConkey agar (Oxoid) with a 5 µg ciprofloxacin disc (Oxoid) to screen for fluoroquinolone resistance. Due to the higher concentration of bacteria in sewage, direct swab plating was employed for wastewater samples on to the same agars. Bacterial species identification was achieved using matrix-assisted laser desorption ionization time of flight (MALDI-TOF) mass spectrometry (Bruker microflex).

2.3. Antibiotic susceptibility testing

Antibiotic susceptibility testing was performed on all Enterobacterales identified from sewage and water samples according to EUCAST guidelines (EUCAST version 11.0, 2021). Antibiotics included ampicillin (10 µg), ceftazidime (30 µg), cefepime (10 µg), cefepime/clavulanic acid (10 µg/1 µg), ceftazidime (10 µg), cefotaxime (5 µg), ertapenem (10 µg), meropenem (10 µg), gentamicin (10 µg), kanamycin (30 µg), streptomycin (10 µg), tetracycline (30 µg), chloramphenicol (30 µg), nalidixic acid (30 µg), ciprofloxacin (5 µg) and trimethoprim (5 µg). EUCAST breakpoint were used to interpret the results with the exception of nalidixic acid, streptomycin, tetracycline and kanamycin for which CLSI breakpoints were applied. *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ATCC 700603 and *E. coli* ATCC 25922 were used in each batch as quality controls.

Antibiogram profiling was followed by real time PCR. Phenotypic ESBL producers were screened for the presence of ESBL genes including *bla*_{CTX-M-group1}, *bla*_{CTX-M-group2} and *bla*_{CTX-M-group9} (Birkett et al., 2007). Real time PCR was also performed on isolates that displayed reduced susceptibility to the carbapenem antibiotics. This included testing for the presence of *bla*_{OXA-48}, *bla*_{KPC} and *bla*_{NDM} (Manchanda et al., 2011; Swayne et al., 2011). Additionally, the presence of *bla*_{VIM} and *bla*_{IMP} were also assessed using a duplex assay from the National Carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales Reference Laboratory Service, Ireland (Unpublished data). All primer and probe sequences, as well as the cycling conditions used are outlined in Supplementary Table 2. Potential duplicate isolates were removed at this point by comparing the antibiograms and PCR results of bacteria of the same species from the same sample.

2.4. Whole genome sequencing

A total of 146 individual bacterial isolates were selected for whole genome sequencing. This encompassed 114 isolates originating from waters and 32 isolates from sewage sources. All carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales were selected for sequencing irrespective of sample origin ($n = 37$). The selection basis for the remaining 109 isolates included the creation of four heatmaps displaying antibiotic susceptibility data for all isolates from each of the four local authority areas. Using cluster analysis, isolates of the same species and highly similar antibiograms from waters and sewage sources were flagged. These isolates were separated out into carbapenem non-susceptible (resistant and intermediate) isolates, phenotypic ESBL producers and those without either type of beta-lactam resistance. This enabled the selection of further isolates of interest for sequencing including ESBL producers (87 *bla*_{CTX-M} positive, 3 phenotypic ESBL producers but *bla*_{CTX-M} negative) and carbapenem resistant ($n = 16$) Enterobacterales, in addition to a

small subset of isolates that did not display ESBL production or reduced susceptibility to carbapenems ($n = 3$).

DNA extraction was carried out using the EZ1 Advanced XL machine with the EZ1 DNA tissue kit (Qiagen) on 48 isolates. The majority ($n = 35$) included a pre-enrichment, which involved the addition of 2–3 colonies from a pure culture to 2 mL of buffered peptone water, incubated shaking at 37 °C overnight. This enrichment broth was subsequently centrifuged at 7500 rpm for 5 minutes. The pellet was resuspended in buffer G2 and the protocol was followed according to the manufacturer's instructions. These isolates were sequenced using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 in Oxford's Genomics Centre (PE150). The remaining 13 isolates had no pre-enrichment step and were sequenced using the Illumina MiSeq (PE300). Due to supply issues, DNA extraction was also carried out using the QIAamp DNA Mini Kit (Qiagen) for the majority of isolates ($n = 98$). This process also included a pre-enrichment step as described previously. The concentrated pellet was resuspended in buffer ATL and the protocol was followed according to the manufacturer's instructions. These isolates were also sequenced using the Illumina NovaSeq 6000 platform (PE150).

The bacterial genomes were assembled and analysed bioinformatically using the tormes pipeline (v1.2.1) (Quijada et al., 2019). Trimmomatic (v0.39) was used to remove any sequencing adapters and filter the reads per quality (Leading: 25, Trailing: 25) and size (minlen: 125 for PE150, minlen: 225 for PE300) (Bolger et al., 2014). The average cleaned data size for the bacterial strains analysed on the Illumina Novaseq 6000 ($n = 133$) was 1.33 ± 0.17 Gb. The average cleaned data size for the bacterial strains analysed on the Illumina MiSeq ($n = 13$) was 0.31 ± 0.06 Gb. Bacterial genome assembly was carried out using SPAdes (v3.15.3) (Prjibelski et al., 2020). The assembled draft genomes were of an average depth of $254 \pm 34x$ and $59 \pm 11x$ for the bacterial strains sequenced on the Illumina Novaseq 6000 and the MiSeq respectively. Taxonomic identification was calculated based on k-mers, using Kraken2 (v2.1.1) with the MiniKraken2 database (v.1) (Wood and Salzberg, 2014). In the case of isolates with a low percentage identity at species level, the 16S gene was isolated using ContEst16S (Lee et al., 2017) and identity was confirmed using BLAST Nucleotide with the default parameters. The assembled genomes were assigned multilocus sequenced types (MLST) using the tool mlst (v2.19.0) (Seemann, <https://github.com/tseemann/mlst>), based on scanning the contigs against the PubMLST database (Jolley et al., 2018). The assembled contigs were scanned for the presence of antibiotic resistance genes using the tool Abricate (v0.9.9) against the CARD (McArthur et al., 2013), ResFinder (Zankari et al., 2012) and ARG-ANNOT (Gupta et al., 2014) databases. Only hits with coverage and identity >90% were considered. Using Abricate, the assembled genomes were also screened against the PlasmidFinder (Carattoli et al., 2014) databases for the identification of plasmids. As before, only hits with >90% identity and coverage were kept. All databases used with Abricate were most recently updated on the 27th of March 2021 (Seemann, <https://github.com/tseemann/abricate>).

E. coli and *Klebsiella* isolates with repeated sequence types were compared using the genome comparator tool on the BIGSdb platform (Jolley et al., 2018). This tool performs pairwise allele alignments at 2513 loci for *E. coli* and 694 loci for *Klebsiella* between the submitted genomes. The 'GrapeTree' tool (Zhou et al., 2018) was used to visualise core genome MLST comparisons through creation of minimum spanning trees. All sequenced *E. coli* genomes are housed on the Escherichia database on PubMLST (v1) (<https://pubmlst.org/organisms/escherichia-spp/>), while the sequenced *Klebsiella* isolates were uploaded to the BIGSdb *Klebsiella* Pasteur MLST database (v1.30.0) (<http://bigsd.bpasteur.fr/klebsiella>). The identifier number for each of the sequenced isolates on these databases, along with the European nucleotide database are outlined in Supplementary Table 9.

3. Results

3.1. Faecal indicator organisms

Examination of the Colilert results was carried out in conjunction with potential contributing factors including distance to discharges, average

rainfall over a 7-day period prior to sample collection and agricultural activity (Fig. 1, Supplementary Table 3). The data was categorised as low (green), medium (yellow) and high (red) for each of the variables. Rainfall, coliforms and *E. coli* measurements were categorised based on low to high numerical values. In contrast, the distance to discharges were categorised based on risk, with smaller distances receiving high risk designation (red) versus longer distances being regarded as low risk (green). Agricultural activity was categorised at an electoral district level as low, medium and high based on maps of potential contributing sources of antibiotic resistance dissemination, created previously by Chique et al. (2019). The data generated during the initial point prevalence sampling campaign was also included for seasonal comparison (Hooban et al., 2021).

Cork local authority area harbored many discharges in close proximity to samples collected with three sampling sites identified as having 4

different discharges nearby. Although the rainfall levels were classified as low (<5 mm) for both the point prevalence (PP) and longitudinal survey 2 (LS2) samples, the seasonal aspects largely differed. This was reflected in the overall lower levels of coliforms and *E. coli* detected in the PP samples collected in May/June 2019 versus the LS2 samples obtained in October/November 2019. Collection of the longitudinal survey 1 (LS1) samples took place in November 2020 with medium rainfall (5.0–9.9 mm) for all samples. Direct comparison with the LS2 data revealed that the faecal indicator levels varied between the 14 sites collected across both periods. A total of 10 samples from the LS1 contained very high coliform levels (≥ 1000 MPN/100 mL) versus 6 collected during LS2.

Fingal had the lowest number of discharges deemed in close proximity to the sample collection sites. Seawater and estuarine waters were the only natural water types included in this region, with the latter harboring much

Fig. 1. Tile plot displaying categorical data of potential contributing sources versus coliform and *E. coli* results. Grey tiles indicate the absence of data. Red tiles indicate ≥ 1000 MPN/100 mL coliforms/*E. coli*, ≥ 10 mm rainfall average, high agricultural activity and ≤ 0.5 km from the sample collection point to a discharge/storm water overflow. Yellow tiles indicate between 251 and 999 MPN/100 mL coliforms/*E. coli*, 5.0–9.9 mm rainfall average, medium agricultural activity and between 0.6 and 1 km from the sample collection point to a discharge/storm water overflow. Green indicates ≤ 250 MPN/100 mL coliforms/*E. coli*, <5 mm rainfall average, low agricultural activity and ≥ 1.1 km distance from the sample collection point to a discharge/storm water overflow. UWWD = Urban wastewater discharge. Raw data relating to this figure is outlined in Supplementary Table 3.

higher coliform and *E. coli* levels overall. Sample collection was carried out across different seasons with the PP survey completed in April 2019, LS1 in October 2019 and LS2 in September 2020. All samples within the PP and LS1 sample collection periods had low average rainfall in the week prior to sample collection. In contrast LS2 samples had low ($n = 4$) and medium ($n = 8$) rainfall levels. However, the medium rainfall only translated to categorically higher faecal indicator levels in two samples across the longitudinal survey periods.

Galway City had low agricultural activity and no raw sewage discharges in close proximity to any of the samples collected. However, it harbored the highest number of storm water overflows categorised as high risk (≤ 0.5 km, $n = 10$) across the four local authority areas. The average rainfall over seven days prior to sample collection was categorised as medium for each sample collected within LS1 ($n = 14$) and the majority of samples collected in the PP survey (5/6), but varied from low (2/14) to high (4/14) in LS2. The coliform levels detected in 11/17 (65%) of the sites across one ($n = 9$) or both ($n = 2$) of the longitudinal survey sampling periods were categorised as high (≥ 1000 MPN/100 mL). PP samples were collected between November 2018 and January 2019, whereas the LS1 samples were collected in August 2019 and the LS2 in February/March 2020.

Galway County local authority area displayed low to medium agricultural activity and contained the highest number of raw sewage discharges in close proximity (≤ 0.5 km) to sampling points ($n = 4$). Coliform and *E. coli* levels varied from low to high in samples located close to raw sewage discharges with low to medium rainfall across the three sampling periods. A seasonal approach was applied through collection of the PP samples in January/February 2019, LS1 in September 2019 and the LS2 in March and July 2020.

3.2. Antibiotic-resistant Enterobacterales

A total of 419 antibiotic-resistant Enterobacterales (348 water, 71 sewage) were isolated from all samples. The majority of isolates were *E. coli* ($n = 346$) followed by *Klebsiella* spp. ($n = 40$), *Enterobacter* spp. ($n = 13$) and *Citrobacter* spp. ($n = 13$). The remaining isolates included 3 *Morganella morganii*, 3 *Raoultella ornithinolytica* and 1 *E. albertii*.

Multi-drug antibiotic resistance was widely detected across all sample types (Fig. 2). Isolates originating from hospital sewage displayed the highest percentage of resistance to the majority of beta-lactam antibiotics including cefpodoxime (86%), ceftazidime (71%), ertapenem (51%) and cefoxitin (40%). Similarly, resistance to nalidixic acid (80%), gentamicin (60%) and kanamycin (43%) also featured highest amongst hospital sewage isolates. Estuarine waters ranked highest for the percentage of resistant isolates to cefotaxime (82%), ciprofloxacin (74%) and streptomycin (56%). Direct comparison of isolates from waters versus sewage (Supplementary Fig. 1), revealed a higher percentage of water isolates displayed resistance to chloramphenicol (19% water, 9% sewage), streptomycin (41% water, 34% sewage) and tetracycline (50% water, 43% sewage). Conversely, sewage isolates showed predominant resistance to cefotaxime (76% sewage, 65% water) and ertapenem (36% sewage, 24% water). The lowest levels of resistance across all sample types was evident for meropenem (3% water, 6% sewage) and chloramphenicol (19% water, 9% sewage).

3.3. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing Enterobacterales

ESBL producers were identified by phenotypic ESBL production in 92/118 (78%) waters and 18/36 (50%) sewage samples. Many samples comprised of more than one ESBL producer, which included 185 Enterobacterales that

Fig. 2. Percentage of isolates from each sample type that displayed a resistant phenotype to the panel of 15 antibiotics tested. DWTP = drinking water treatment plant, WWTP = wastewater treatment plant.

harbored *bla*_{CTX-M-group1} and 59 that contained *bla*_{CTX-M-group9}. Whole genome sequencing of a selection of ESBLs ($n = 92$) revealed that *bla*_{CTX-M-15} ($n = 63$) was the most frequently detected ESBL gene, followed by 17 isolates that harbored *bla*_{CTX-M-27} (Fig. 4). Additional *bla*_{CTX-M} genes were also identified to a lesser extent including *bla*_{CTX-M-1} ($n = 4$), *bla*_{CTX-M-14} ($n = 4$), *bla*_{CTX-M-55} ($n = 3$), *bla*_{CTX-M-3} ($n = 3$), *bla*_{CTX-M-32} ($n = 1$) and *bla*_{CTX-M-9} ($n = 1$). Further ESBL types detected from sequenced isolates included *bla*_{SHV-12} ($n = 5$), *bla*_{SHV-106} ($n = 3$) and *bla*_{OXA-17} ($n = 2$).

3.4. Carbapenem resistant Enterobacterales

A total of 83 water (24%) and 31 sewage isolates (44%) displayed resistance to ertapenem alone or in combination with meropenem. One or more Enterobacterales harboring a carbapenemase gene were isolated from 18 water and 5 sewage samples. The majority of these isolates contained *bla*_{OXA-48} ($n = 18$), followed by *bla*_{NDM} ($n = 14$), *bla*_{KPC} ($n = 4$) and *bla*_{OXA-484} ($n = 1$) (Fig. 3). River water had the highest number of carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales detected ($n = 12$) in 7 individual samples. NDM-producers were solely detected in waters with the exception of one isolate from airport sewage.

3.5. Additional antibiotic resistances detected using whole genome sequencing

A total of 146 bacterial isolates were sequenced encompassing 114 water and 32 sewage isolates. The antibiogram profiles along with the resistance genes identified using ResFinder were combined in Fig. 4. The majority of isolates ($n = 138$) harbored one or more beta-lactamase gene. This included most commonly *bla*_{CTX-M-15} (48 water, 14 sewage), *bla*_{TEM-1B} (43 water, 10 sewage) and *bla*_{OXA-1} (15 water, 6 sewage). Comparison of the carbapenemase genes detected with the phenotypic data revealed that *bla*_{OXA-48} ($n = 18$) and *bla*_{OXA-484} producers ($n = 1$) displayed resistance to ertapenem in all isolates and an intermediate phenotype to meropenem for the majority of isolates ($n = 17$). Antibiotics against which bacteria display an intermediate phenotype are not normally prescribed due to

uncertainty surrounding therapeutic success. In contrast, *bla*_{NDM} isolates displayed resistance to both ertapenem and meropenem in 13/14 isolates. Similarly, all four *bla*_{KPC} producers showed dual resistance to both carbapenem antibiotics. All NDM-producing isolates harbored the *ble-MLB* gene which confers bleomycin resistance, identified using the CARD database.

Sulphonamide resistance genes *sul1*, *sul2* and *sul3* were the next most common resistance type following the beta-lactamase genes, identified within 92 isolates. The majority of isolates also harbored one or more aminoglycoside ($n = 86$) and trimethoprim ($n = 80$) resistance gene. The presence of these resistance genes was reflected in the phenotypic data with 79/80 isolates that contained one or more *dfra* genes displaying trimethoprim resistance. Thirteen different resistance genes were detected that confer reduced susceptibility to aminoglycosides. One pattern that emerged through comparison of the phenotypic and genotypic data was the presence the *aph* (*3'*)-*Ib* gene alone or in combination with the *aph*(6)-*Id* gene conferred streptomycin resistance in 49/52 isolates. However, many of these isolates also harbored additional aminoglycoside resistance genes. The *tetA*, *tetB* and *tetD* genes were detected in 71 sequenced isolates, of which 70 displayed tetracycline resistance. The *fosA* gene which reduces susceptibility to fosfomycin was identified in 37 of the sequenced Enterobacterales. The majority of these isolates were *Klebsiella* spp. ($n = 27$), followed by *Enterobacter* spp. ($n = 6$), *E. coli* ($n = 3$) and 1 *Raoultella*.

Some of the rarer antibiotic resistance genes detected included the *arr3* gene in one *Klebsiella pneumoniae* identified from hospital sewage and the *Inu(F)* gene in an *E. coli* from seawater, which confer resistance to rifamycin and lincomycin respectively. A total of four isolates also harbored *mcr9* including one *E. coli* from river water, along with two *Enterobacter* and one *Raoultella* isolate from sewage.

3.6. Plasmid analysis

The majority of sequenced isolates harbored one or more plasmids (140/146). Plasmid replicon types detected included many different Inc. and Col types, including Inc. (FIA, FIB, FII) and Col (RNAI, MG828, 440I,

Fig. 3. Carbapenemase genes detected within Enterobacterales isolated from different water and sewage sources. WWTP = wastewater treatment plant.

Table 1

Summarised results including number of isolates of individual species from different samples, sequence types and plasmids detected for all sequenced isolates.

Sample type	Species	No. of isolates	Sequence type	Plasmids
Seawater	<i>Escherichia coli/albertii</i>	38 – <i>E. albertii</i>	10 (3), 34 (2), 38 (2), 58 (1), 95 (1), 131 (8), 162 (2), 167 (2), 224 (1), 382 (1), 394 (1), 410 (2), 540 (1), 648 (3), 744 (1), 1015 (1), 1193 (1), 2659 (1), 4121 (1), 10,302 (1), unknown (3)	IncFIB (26), 2 IncFIB (1), IncFII (22), 2 IncFII (1), Col (13), 2 Col (6), 3 Col (6), 4 Col (2), 5 Col (1), IncFIC(FII) (11), IncFIA (17), IncI (1), IncB/O/K/Z (1), 2 IncB/O/K/Z (1), IncX (3), IncR (1), IncY (5), IncP1 (1), IncN (1), IncL (1), 0 plasmids (2)
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	9	8 (1), 17 (3), 289 (2), 307 (1), 323 (1), 1933 (1)	IncFIB (8), 2 IncFIB (1), IncFIA (2), Col (3), 2 Col (1), IncFII (5), IncL (4), IncR (3)
	<i>Enterobacter hormaechei</i>	1	190 (1)	2 Col (1)
River	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	25	10 (3), 38 (3), 69 (1), 88 (1), 101 (2), 127 (1), 131 (2), 354 (1), 394 (2), 405 (3), 410 (2), 635 (1), 8530 (1), unknown (2)	IncFIB (16), 2 IncFIB (1), IncFII (13), 2 IncFII (1), Col (7), 2 Col (1), 3 Col (1) 4 Col (4), 5 Col (1), IncFIC(FII) (3), IncFIA (8), IncI (8), IncB/O/K/Z (4), IncX (2), IncY (3), IncQ (1), p0111 (3), 2 IncHI2 (1), RepA_pKPC-CAV1321 (1), pENTAS02 (1), 0 plasmids (2)
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	9	8 (1), 17 (3), 289 (2), 307 (1), 323 (1), 1933 (1)	IncFIB (4), 2 IncFIB (1), 3 IncFIB (1), IncFIA (2), Col (1), 2 Col (1), IncFII (1), 2 IncFII (1), IncHI (2), IncL (3), IncQ (1)
Estuary	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	18	10 (2), 69 (1), 88 (1), 131 (3), 167 (1), 405 (5), 410 (1), 648 (1), 1193 (1), 1294 (1), 4213 (1)	IncFIB (12), 2 IncFIB (1), IncFII (11), 2 IncFII (1), Col (4), 2 Col (5), 3 Col (4), 5 Col (1), IncFIC(FII) (4), IncFIA (9), IncI (6), IncX (2), p0111 (4)
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	5	17 (1), 231 (1), 309 (1), 323 (1), 5258 (1).	IncFIB (4), 2 IncFIB (1), IncFIA (2), Col (2), 2 Col (1), IncFII (2), 2 IncFII (1), IncHI (1), IncL (1), IncR (1)
Estuarine lagoon	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	38 (1), 131 (2)	IncFIB (2), IncFII (1), 2 IncFII (1), Col (1), 5 Col (1), IncFIA (1), IncX (1), 0 plasmids (1)
	<i>Enterobacter hormaechei</i>	1	190 (1)	IncL (1)
Lake	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	2	59 (1), 224 (1)	IncFIB (1), IncFII (1), 4 Col (1), IncFIC(FII) (1), IncL (1), IncB/O/K/Z (1)
Drinking water treatment plant influent	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	131 (2), 348 (1)	IncFIB (3), IncFII (3), Col (2), IncFIA (3), IncI (1), IncY (1)
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1	17 (1)	Col (1), IncFIA (1), IncFII (1)
Hospital sewage	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	5	69 (1), 131 (2), 2562 (1), 6280 (1)	IncFIB (4), IncFII (1), 2 IncFII (2), Col (2), 2 Col (1), 4 Col (1), IncFIC(FII) (1), IncFIA (2), IncI (1), 0 plasmids (1)
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1	17 (1)	2 Col (1), 2 IncFIB (1), IncFII (1), IncR (1), IncN (1)
	<i>Klebsiella oxytoca</i>	3	2 (1), 88 (1), 135 (1)	IncFIB (1), IncFII (1), 2 Col (2), IncR (1), IncL (1)
	<i>Enterobacter kobei/cloacae</i>	1 – <i>E. kobei</i> 1 – <i>E. cloacae</i>	<i>E. kobei</i> – 910 (1) <i>E. cloacae</i> – unknown (1)	IncFIA (1), IncFII (1), IncL (1), IncR (1), 2 Col (2), 2 IncHI2 (1), pKPC-CAV1321 (1), RepA_pKPC-CAV1321 (1)
	<i>Citrobacter freundii</i>	3	64 (1), 150 (1), 166 (1)	IncL (1), 3 Col (1), IncFII (1), 2 IncFIB (2), 2 IncFII (1), pKPC-CAV1321 (2)
Wastewater treatment plant influent	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	7	131 (4), 602 (1), 607 (1), 1193 (1)	IncFIB (5), IncFII (3), Col (4), 2 Col (2), IncFIC(FII) (2), IncFIA (5), IncI (2), IncX (1), IncR (1) IncY (1)
	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	2	37 (1), 323 (1)	IncFIB (2), Col (1), IncFII (2), IncL (1), Inc R (1)
	<i>Enterobacter cloacae/hormaechei</i>	1 – <i>E. cloacae</i> 1 – <i>E. hormaechei</i>	<i>E. cloacae</i> – 910 (1) <i>E. hormaechei</i> – 133 (1)	IncFIA (1), IncFII (1), IncL (1), IncR (1), Col (2), 2 IncHI2 (1), pKPC-CAV1321 (2)
	<i>Raoultella ornithinolytica</i>	1	Unknown (1)	3 Col (1), IncFIB (1), IncFII (1), 2 IncHI2 (1), IncL (1), pKPC-CAV1321 (1)
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	1	167 (1)	IncFIB (1), Col (1), IncFIC(FII) (1), IncFIA (1)
Nursing Home	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1	323 (1)	2 Col (1), IncFIA (1), IncFIB (1), IncFII (1)
	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	3	38 (1), 394 (1), 131 (1)	IncFIB (2), IncFII (2), Col (2), IncFIC(FII) (1), IncFIA (1), IncB/O/K/Z (1),
Airport	<i>Klebsiella pneumoniae</i>	1	76 (1)	IncFIA (1), IncFIB (1)

A number preceding the plasmid name indicates two different types, e.g. 2 IncQ: IncQ1 and IncQ2. The different plasmids that were identified using PlasmidFinder and summarised are listed. **Col:** Col(MG828), Col(pHAD28), Col440II, Col440I, ColRNAI, Col8282, ColE10, ColpVC, Col(BS512), Col(MP18), Col(Ye4449), Col156. **IncFIA:** IncFIA(HI1), IncFIA. **IncFIB:** IncFIB(K)(pCAV1099-114), IncFIB(K), IncFIB(pKPHS1), IncFIB(pNDM-Mar), IncFIB(pQil), IncFIB(K)_Kpn3, IncFIB(pB171), IncFIB(pHCM2), IncFIB(pQil), IncFIB(AP001918). **IncFII:** IncFII(p14), IncFII(pECLA), IncFII(pKP91), IncFII(pRSB107), IncFII(Yp)_Yersenia, IncFII(pECLA), IncFII_pKP91, IncFII(29)_pUTI89, FII(pBK30683), IncFII(pCRY), IncFII(pCoo), IncFII(pHN7A8), IncFII(pAMA1167-NDM-5), IncFII, IncFII_pSFO. **IncHI:** IncHI1B(CIT)_pNDM, IncHI1B(pNDM-MAR), IncHI1B(R27), IncHI1A(CIT)_pNDM, IncHI1A. **IncHI2:** IncHI2A, IncHI2. **IncL:** IncL, IncL/M(pOXA-48). **IncB/O/K/Z:** IncB/O/K/Z_1, IncB/O/K/Z_2, IncB/O/K/Z_4. **IncQ:** IncQ1, IncQ2. **IncX:** IncX1, IncX2, IncX3, IncX4.

(B20338, B20377, B20384) that all harbored *bla*_{OXA-48} from waters which spanned a 9.8 km distance in Cork. Similarly, the ST231 isolates were identical (B19819, B19846), and originated from aquatic samples collected over 24 hours from two sites in the same region in Cork. Both isolates

harbored *bla*_{KPC-3} and the collection sites were located 3.3 km apart. The collection of isolates belonging to sequence type ST323 encompassed isolates from sewage (n = 4) and waters (n = 3) across Cork and Galway. The smaller cluster within this group included two genetically

Fig. 5. Heatmap displaying the number of each type of plasmid detected within Enterobacteriales harboring a carbapenemase gene.

indistinguishable isolates with identical antibiograms from the same nursing home, collected 7 months apart (B19023, B19574). The larger cluster included identical *Klebsiella* from river H1 in Cork (B19849) as well as wastewater treatment plant influent (B19326) and an estuarine water (estuary B) in Galway City (B19426).

The complete set of sequenced *E. coli* isolates ($n = 153$) were also compared using cgMLST (Fig. 7). A total of 47 different sequence types (STs) were identified with 18 sequence types repeated by two or more isolates (Supplementary Table 7). Five of the isolates could not be matched with a known sequence type. The most commonly detected sequence types amongst *E. coli* included ST131 ($n = 39$) followed by ST38 ($n = 15$) and ST10 ($n = 12$). There were 9 clusters of two or more identical isolates based on cgMLST comparisons at 2513 loci. Just two isolates belonging to the large ST131 collection (B20400, B20369) were 100% identical and originated from a wastewater treatment plant influent and a seawater located 3.2 km apart in Cork. Similarly, another pair of identical isolates belonging to ST167 originated from sewage (nursing home E, B20148) and waters (estuary B2, B20104) in Galway City. However, the sampling locations were further apart, with a distance of 14.5 km between them. A total of four isolates were identical within the ST410 cluster (B19368, B19398, B19421, B19441). These four isolates all originated from waters around Galway City and spanned four different collection points across 5.6 km. There were two identical carbapenemase producers (B19818,

B19852) collected from waters in a highly polluted region in Cork, located 3.8 km apart. These isolates (ST405) both harbored *bla*_{NDM-5} and sample collection took place one day apart.

4. Discussion

4.1. Comparison across sampling periods

Comparison of the longitudinal survey sampling periods to the initial point prevalence survey was carried out at a quantitative level through comparison of the coliforms and *E. coli* detected in waters (Fig. 1). Overall, increased average rainfall over a 7-day period prior to sample collection augmented the coliform levels in some but not all sampling sites. The majority of samples had low (<5 mm) to medium (5.0–9.9 mm) rainfall, making it difficult to fully elucidate the significance of increased rainfall. Conflicting evidence has been previously reported in relation to the impact of heavy rainfall on coliform levels in natural waters. Sampson et al. (2006) reported no relationship between rainfall levels and the concentration of coliforms and *E. coli* detected at 15 beaches in the United States following at least 6 mm of rain during a ‘rainfall event’ in the preceding 24 hours. These beaches were monitored between May to September over the course of two years (2003–2004). In contrast, Kim et al. (2013) demonstrated a correlation between the increased accumulative rainfall in the preceding

Fig. 6. Minimum spanning tree depicting core genome multilocus sequence typing comparison across sequenced *Klebsiella* isolates ($n = 52$). The black circles indicate clusters that were previously identified in the point prevalence survey (Hooban et al., 2021), while the red circles highlight newly identified clusters. The circles are colour coded to indicate the local authority region: Galway city = blue; Galway county = pink; Fingal = green; Cork = orange. The darker colour indicates isolates from sewage origin while the lighter colours indicate water origin. The numbers between the nodes represents the number of locus allele differences between isolates.

1 to 4 days, and the levels of faecal indicator organisms in 34 samples from two sites along the Han River in Korea. These samples were collected between July 2010 and February 2011. Various contributing factors may be responsible for these contrasting findings including the larger dilutional effect and higher salt concentration in seawater, the presence of faecal sources (anthropogenic, agricultural, wildlife) surrounding the sample collection site, and sample collection at varying times of the year.

During this study only four water samples were collected following a period of high rainfall (≥ 10 mm), all located in Galway City. All four displayed higher levels of coliforms and *E. coli* when compared to other sample collection periods in which rainfall was categorised as low to medium. Notably, storm water overflows were located within 1.5 km of all four seawater samples. All four sites were regarded as low agricultural activity at an electoral district level, indicative that the higher coliform concentrations during wet conditions may be due to anthropogenic discharges. Previous studies have demonstrated that stormy weather promotes antibiotic resistance dissemination through activation of storm water overflows and agricultural runoff (Almakki et al., 2019; Eramo et al., 2017). An important consideration when interpreting faecal indicator bacterial levels is that *E. coli* concentrations can significantly vary throughout the day, previously demonstrated by Wyer et al. (2018). These samples were collected at one point in time, at a maximum of three times per site. Intensive sample collection at fewer sites during more extreme weather events is needed to fully establish the significance of increased rainfall at a particular site.

ESBL producers were present in the majority of samples across all sampling periods, indicative of its natural and widespread persistence in the environment across all seasons (Hooban et al., 2020). The *bla*_{CTX-M} gene, detected across the majority of water samples, was previously traced back to the chromosome of *Kluyvera* species, which is ubiquitous in the natural

environment (Cantón et al., 2012). The majority of CPE from water samples originated from Cork and Galway city. Carbapenemase detection varied across different times of the year in Cork, with no detection in samples collected in May/June 2019 (Hooban et al., 2021). In contrast, different carbapenemase gene types were detected in both longitudinal survey periods collected in October/November in 2019 and 2020. The consistent detection of CPE was evident in samples collected from Galway City throughout different seasons. OXA-48-producing isolates were identified across all three periods in one or more water samples across the city. The longitudinal survey periods in Galway city both included the detection of NDM producers at 3 individual collection sites. To the authors' knowledge, there have been little to no studies to date examining carbapenemase detection across different seasons in natural waters highlighting an important knowledge gap. Natural water use for recreational purposes would continue throughout the year in Ireland. Therefore, the repeated presence of CPE throughout different seasons represents a public health concern in relation to increased colonisation rates due to ingestion of water (O'Flaherty et al., 2019; Leonard et al., 2018). Although the detection of antibiotic-resistant organisms is beyond the scope of the current EU bathing water monitoring criteria (Directive 2006/7/EC), the repeated detection of CPE demonstrates the need for year round bathing water monitoring to protect public health. Farrell et al. (2021) also echoed the need for year-long bathing water monitoring, and incorporation of antibiotic resistance detection to the bathing water directive based on a European wide scoping literature review.

4.2. Antibiotic resistance across different sample types

Multi-drug resistant isolates were detected in all sample types, inclusive of sewage and natural waters. Isolates from hospital sewage displayed the

Fig. 7. Minimum spanning tree portraying core genome multilocus sequence typing comparison across sequenced *Escherichia* isolates ($n = 153$). The black circles indicate clusters that were previously identified in the point prevalence survey (Hooban et al., 2021), while the red circles highlight newly identified clusters. The circles are colour coded to indicate the local authority region: Galway city = blue; Galway county = pink; Fingal = green; Cork = orange. The darker colour indicates isolates from sewage origin while the lighter colours indicate water origin. The numbers between the nodes represents the number of locus allele differences between isolates.

highest percentage of resistant isolates to most beta-lactam, aminoglycoside and quinolone antibiotics (Fig. 2). Beta-lactams were the most frequently prescribed antibiotics in Ireland in 2019, with the penicillins used at a national average of 38.6 defined daily dose (DDD) per 100 bed-days used (BDU) within hospitals (Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2020). Cephalosporins, monobactams and carbapenems were prescribed at an average of 9 DDD per 100BDU, increasing from 8.4 in 2018. Aminoglycosides and quinolones ranked lower at 3.7 and 3.3 DDD per 100BDU respectively.

Similarly to previous findings in the point prevalence survey (Hooban et al., 2021), tetracycline and ciprofloxacin resistance were observed at a higher percentage in water versus sewage isolates (Supplementary Fig. 1). The possible explanation for this was outlined previously by Hooban et al. (2021), including the common use of tetracyclines in veterinary medicine (Health products regulatory authority, 2019) and the persistent nature of ciprofloxacin in wastewater (Kumar et al., 2019). Ciprofloxacin was detected at levels exceeding the predicted no-effect concentrations (PNECs) in Irish wastewater treatment plant effluents previously (Rodríguez-Mozaz et al., 2020; Monahan et al., 2021). PNECs were established for individual antibiotics in an attempt to understand the maximum antibiotic concentration, above which, antibiotic resistance development may occur (Bengtsson-Palme and Larsson, 2016). These values were estimated using the minimum inhibitory concentrations from EUCAST and can be used to define acceptable antibiotic concentrations in environmental discharges.

Interestingly, a higher percentage of water isolates also displayed resistance to chloramphenicol and streptomycin. Chloramphenicol was banned from veterinary medicine in Europe in 1994 and can only be administered to animals that will not be used for food purposes (European Food Safety Authority, 2018). However, it is naturally produced by *Streptomyces venezuelae*, which is ubiquitous in soil and the environment (Schwarz

et al., 2004). Chloramphenicol acetyltransferases, encoded by *cat* genes, confer enzymatic inactivation of the antibiotic. In this study, the presence of *cat* genes were detected within 18 isolates (16 water, 2 sewage). However, just ten of these isolates displayed resistance to chloramphenicol. The *floR* gene which confers resistance to florfenicol, was detected in eight isolates, all originating from water (Lu et al., 2018). The florfenicol antibiotic is a derivative of chloramphenicol which is solely used in animals, which may indicate agricultural runoff in close proximity to these sampling areas. Five of the eight strains harbored *floR* in the absence of a *cat* gene, of which four displayed chloramphenicol resistance.

Streptomycin is also derived from an environmental soil bacterium, *Streptomyces griseus* (de Lima Procópio et al., 2012), and therefore the natural resistome in the environment may account for some of the resistance seen amongst water isolates. Aminoglycosides only accounted for a small proportion of antibiotics (6.1%) used in veterinary medicine in Ireland in 2019 (Health products regulatory authority, 2019). An interesting observation in relation to streptomycin was the presence of *aph(3'')-Ib* alone or in combination with *aph(6)-Id* (also known as *strB*) conferred streptomycin resistance in 49/52 isolates. However, these resistance genes were equally distributed across sequenced sewage and water isolates. This indicates that more non-specific mechanisms of resistance may be at play in the water isolates such as ribosomal mutations or efflux pump activity (Lyu et al., 2019).

4.3. Antibiotic resistance of critical clinical concern

Some antibiotic resistance genes detected in environmental isolates are of significant clinical concern, including the detection of carbapenemase and fosfomycin resistance genes. According to clinical surveillance data

from 2018, *bla*_{OXA-48} was the most common carbapenemase gene detected in cases of colonisation and infection in Ireland (Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2019). This was echoed amongst environmental isolates, in which 18 harbored *bla*_{OXA-48}, indicative that similar resistance types are in circulation across clinical and natural environments. OXA-48 conferred reduced susceptibility to ertapenem and meropenem in most isolates making them unsuitable for treatment (Fig. 4). Additionally, 13 of the 18 isolates harbored the *fosA* gene, also reducing the potency of fosfomycin and further limiting potential treatment options. An OXA-48-like carbapenemase (*bla*_{OXA-484}) was also detected in one *E. coli* isolate (B19837) from river water in Cork belonging to sequence type ST410. This isolate displayed a non-susceptible phenotype to all antibiotics tested apart from chloramphenicol. OXA-484 has not been reported in the most recent surveillance reports published by the carbapenemase reference laboratory in Ireland based on data from 2017 to quarter 2 of 2019 (Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2019). However, its most closely related variants OXA-181/232 have been reported in 15 patients within the first half of 2019.

NDM was the second most commonly detected carbapenemase (Fig. 3), with the majority of isolates collected from waters (13/14) and identified as *E. coli* (13/14). All the NDM producers also harbored the *ble*-*MBL* gene which confers bleomycin resistance. The presence of both genes on one operon, separated by just 3 base pairs was previously demonstrated by Dörtet et al. (2012). The *ble*-*MBL* gene confers decreased susceptibility to bleomycin, which is used in cancer treatment. This combination is a significant clinical concern as the use of bleomycin in a hospital setting may select for NDM-producing isolates in immunocompromised individuals. Bleomycin is naturally produced by *Streptomyces verticillus* isolated from soil (Umezawa et al., 1966), and therefore many environmental strains naturally express *ble* resistance genes (Shen et al., 2002). A metagenomics study was previously performed examining activated sludge, which revealed wastewater to be a large reservoir of bleomycin resistance genes (Mori et al., 2008). Further investigations of soils and waters as reservoirs and transmission routes of bleomycin resistance genes are needed.

The final type of carbapenemase gene detected was *bla*_{KPC}, found within two *Klebsiella* isolates from waters (KPC-3; B19819, B19846) and two isolates of different species from the same hospital sewage sample (KPC-2; B20091, B20093). Interestingly, the two KPC-3 producers from waters displayed identical antibiograms with resistance to all antibiotics except tetracyclines (Fig. 4). Thus, these aquatic isolates would be exceptionally difficult to treat if they potentially caused an infection in humans or animals. Whole genome sequencing analysis revealed an array of antibiotic resistance genes within these isolates including beta-lactam, aminoglycoside, sulphonamide, fosfomycin and quinolone resistance genes. The KPC-2 producers had varying resistance profiles and also did not contain any overlapping plasmids potentially indicating chromosomal origin. KPC is the second most commonly identified carbapenemase detected through surveillance of colonisation and infections in Irish hospitals (Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2019).

4.4. Future antibiotic resistance gene threats

The natural aquatic environment represents ideal conditions where ubiquitous, non-pathogenic bacteria come in contact with clinically significant pathogens (Allen et al., 2010). This environment presents the opportunity for the potential transfer of antibiotic resistance genes from harmless bacteria to virulent and potentially pathogenic bacteria. A recent study by Zhang et al. (2021) characterised different antibiotic resistance genes into current and future threats based on pathogenicity, human-associated enrichment, and the potential of gene transfer. A total of 5 different antibiotic resistance genes classified as emerging threats were detected in water and/or sewage samples in this study. These included *bla*_{CMY-2} (*n* = 1), *bla*_{SHV} (*n* = 31), *aadA* (*n* = 54), *erm(B)* (*n* = 5) and *catA* (*n* = 14) which confer beta-lactam, aminoglycoside, macrolide and chloramphenicol resistance respectively. According to Zhang et al. (2021), some of these resistance genes have only recently been detected in the ESKAPE pathogens

group, including SHV, *ermB* and *catA*. Amongst the environmental isolates, SHV was mainly detected in *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates (26/31), with the remainder including SHV-12 detection (5/31) in 2 *Enterobacter*, 2 *E. coli* and 1 *Raoultella* isolate. The detection of this beta-lactamase gene in environmental isolates belonging to the ESKAPE pathogens group further illustrates the need for more regular monitoring of the aquatic environment for the presence of clinically significant antibiotic-resistant organisms. Frequent monitoring would aid in the establishment of the origins of different resistance genes and assist in the surveillance of future emerging threats. The findings in this paper illustrate how environmental monitoring would significantly benefit from genomics based analysis allowing for the detection of emerging resistance gene threats, rather than relying solely on a culture-based approach for resistance detection.

4.5. Sequence types detected and core genome MLST comparisons

Examination of the sequence types detected revealed the presence of *E. coli* and *Klebsiella* strains associated with multi-drug resistance typically circulating in clinical environments. A prime example includes gut coloniser *E. coli* ST131 which is frequently linked to CTX-M production and fluoroquinolone resistance (Whitmer et al., 2019). This sequence type is commonly identified from urinary tract infections (Muller et al., 2021), but has also been isolated in cases of sepsis (Paramita et al., 2020). The majority of *E. coli* sequence type ST131 isolates that were selected for sequencing from this study harbored one CTX-M variant (23/24), highlighting the similarities amongst strains in the clinical and natural environments. A study by Hu et al. (2013) identified sequence types of CTX-M-producing *E. coli* from a variety of sources including water, swine and humans. Interestingly, sequence types ST131 and ST38 were both solely detected from waters and human sources, potentially indicating anthropogenic activity as the source of these isolates in the environment. In the longitudinal survey sampling periods, ST38 was detected in 5 individual waters samples as well as one sample collected from airport sewage. Three of the ST38 isolates harbored an OXA-48, while one harbored NDM-5, both of which have previously been reported in this sequence type from human isolates (Abid et al., 2021, Brehony et al., 2019, Khan et al., 2018).

Core genome MLST comparisons identified two identical *E. coli* isolates belonging to the ST131 collection (B20400, B20369) originating from a wastewater treatment plant influent and a seawater in Cork, collected on the same day. These isolates shared identical resistance genes conferring reduced susceptibility to aminoglycosides, tetracyclines, trimethoprim and beta-lactam antibiotics. The close proximity of these sites (3.2 km) and the location of the seawater sample downstream of the discharge from this plant potentially indicates that this bacteria originated from human wastewater. However, it was not detected in the effluent sample collected on the same day from this wastewater treatment plant. An additional *E. coli* sequence type (ST167) contained two identical isolates from sewage (B20148; nursing home E) and water (B20104; estuary B2) in Galway City. This analysis indicates that the detection of this particular isolate in estuarine waters originated from human sewage sources. These two isolates also harbored identical antibiotic resistance genes, detected using ResFinder. Although *bla*_{CTX-M-15} and *bla*_{OXA-1} were the only beta-lactamase genes detected in these isolates, this sequence type is commonly associated with NDM carriage in the clinical environment (Wu et al., 2019). However, two *E. coli* (B20127, B20159) from seawaters surrounding a wastewater treatment plant in Galway City belonging to ST167 harbored *bla*_{NDM-5}. These two isolates differed from each other by 107 loci, and from the identical nursing home (B20148) and estuarine water (B20104) isolates by over 500 loci.

A significant pattern emerged in relation to *bla*_{NDM-5} detection more frequently in *E. coli* sequence type ST405 in comparison to any other sequence type. A total of 7/9 isolates belonging to this sequence type harbored NDM-5, and all originated from aquatic samples. This sequence type was previously linked to NDM-5 carriage in clinical isolates reported from Italy (Bitar et al., 2017), Japan (Takayama et al., 2020) and India (Ranjan

et al., 2016). Two of these aquatic isolates were identical (B19818, B19852) based on pairwise allele alignments at 2513 loci from a region in Cork receiving multiple anthropogenic discharges, potentially indicating human origin. These isolates were collected just on day apart and both harbored the same three plasmids including IncFIB, IncI Gamma, and p0111.

Similarly to the *E. coli*, many of the *Klebsiella* sequence types repeatedly detected from the environment mirror those that are commonly identified in cases of human carriage and infection. For example, 5 isolates belonging to ST323, all harboring *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *fosA6* and *fosA7*, were identified from 3 water and 2 sewage samples in this study. This *Klebsiella pneumoniae* sequence type was previously identified harboring KPC-2 from a human sputum sample in China (Gong et al., 2018), and harboring *bla*_{CTX-M-15} from urine samples, along with rectal and wound swabs in Australia (Gorrie et al., 2018). Interestingly, two identical isolates (B19023, B19574) belonging to ST323 were isolated from the same nursing home effluent, collected over 8 months apart. This indicates potential long-term persistence of this bacterium in the gut of the nursing home resident(s), or alternatively persistence of the bacterium in the septic tank housed within the grounds. Repeated environmental contamination through runoff is also a possibility due to the location of the tank on a decline in respect to the nursing home. However, the tank normally remains covered so this possibility is less likely. Both isolates from this nursing home harbored identical resistance genes including *bla*_{CTX-M-15}, *bla*_{SHV-187}, *fosA6*, *fosA7*, *oqxA* and *oqxB*. Both also contained five identical plasmids including Col(pHAD28), Col440II, IncFIA(HII), IncFIB(K) and IncFII(pKP91).

A total of 6 *Klebsiella pneumoniae* ST17 isolates were identified from different water samples. Two of these isolates were identical (B20121, B20134) and harbored *bla*_{OXA-48}. Sample collection took place on the same day just 0.9km apart. Sequence type ST17 was previously reported in ESBL-producing *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolated from human faecal samples in Bulgaria (Markovska et al., 2021). Similarly, a clinical isolate characterised as 'extensively drug resistant' belonging to ST17, harboring KPC from urine, was recently identified in Brazil (Nakamura-Silva et al., 2021). These clinical isolates highlight the pathogenic potential of this particular sequence type.

Sequence type ST309 was the fourth most common *Klebsiella* sequence type detected (B20338, B20377, B20384). Notably, all three *Klebsiella* ST309 isolates originated from polluted waters in different samples from Cork (River H2, River H, Estuary E1), harbored *bla*_{OXA-48}, and were identical based on cgMLST comparisons. Sample collection took place over 24 hours and the three sampling sites were located in close proximity to one another, with a distance of 9.7 km between the two furthest points. All three isolates harbored IncFIB(K) and IncL plasmids. Reports of clinical ST309 *Klebsiella* isolates harboring *bla*_{OXA-48} have previously been published from Ireland (Brehony et al., 2019) and Yemen (Alsharapy et al., 2020). The ST309 isolates in this study were compared to those analysed by Brehony et al. (2019) using cgMLST comparisons. This comparison revealed that between 35 and 37 loci varied between the three isolates from this study and the two OXA-48-producing clinical isolates. This variability indicates significant differences in the core genomes between the clinical and environmental isolates.

A further two identical carbapenemase producers (B19819, B19846) were isolated from the same polluted region in Cork one year prior (2019). Sampling locations (Estuary E, River H) were located just 3.3 km apart and sample collection took place one day apart (Supplementary Table 6). These isolates harbored *bla*_{KPC-3} and belonged to sequence type ST231. Isolate B19846 harbored one additional plasmid (IncFIB(K)), totaling 7 (Fig. 5), and also contained the *df*rA14 trimethoprim resistance gene which was not detected in B19819. This region in Cork receives multiple discharges including storm water overflows and raw sewage discharges from anthropogenic sources.

4.6. Plasmids detection

The potential for widespread dissemination of antibiotic resistance genes of clinical concern amongst environmental isolates is high, due to

the majority of sequenced isolates containing one or more plasmid (140/146). Due to the limitations of short read sequencing it could not be established which antibiotic resistance genes reside on plasmids. However, based on the literature, there are certain plasmids that are commonly linked to the carriage of different clinically significant antibiotic resistance genes. Of particular interest is the carbapenemase resistance genes, and an example of such is the detection of *bla*_{OXA-48} on the IncL plasmid. A total of 15 out of 18 of the OXA-48 isolates in this study also contained this plasmid (Fig. 5). A previous study by Bleichenbacher et al. (2020) detected *bla*_{OXA-48} on an IncL plasmid within *Raoultella ornithinolytica*, isolated from freshwater in Switzerland. In a previous study by Brehony et al. (2019), it was confirmed that 93/109 clinical isolates obtained from Irish hospitals contained both *bla*_{OXA-48}, in addition to the backbone genes for the pOXA-48-like plasmid (IncL-type). Therefore, it may be the case that OXA-48 carriage in the 15 environmental isolates from this study are plasmid-borne. The potential for horizontal gene transfer of the IncL plasmid that harbors *bla*_{OXA-48} has recently been proven to be high amongst clinical isolates in Germany (Hamprecht et al., 2019). Therefore, this plasmid type may harbor a significant proportion of the responsibility for the high number of OXA-48-producing isolates in Irish hospitals, rather than one particular clone. The detection of numerous OXA-48 isolates that harbored the IncL plasmid in this study further demonstrates the overlap between the clinical and natural environments. As mentioned previously, one *E. coli* isolate (B19837) characterised as ST410 from river water harbored an OXA-48-like gene (*bla*_{OXA-484}). A recent study investigated the genetic characteristics of a clinical *E. coli* isolate which harbored *bla*_{OXA-484} also belonging to ST410 (Sommer et al., 2021). They identified carriage of the *bla*_{OXA-484} gene on the IncX3 plasmid, which was also detected in B19837, along with 6 other plasmids. This potentially indicates plasmid carriage of the carbapenemase resistance gene, however further testing is necessary to confirm this.

Comparably, the second most commonly detected carbapenemase gene (*bla*_{NDM}) displayed a similar pattern in which the majority of isolates contained the IncFIB plasmid (11/14). Both *bla*_{NDM-1} and *bla*_{NDM-5} have previously been detected on IncFIB plasmids within isolates of clinical origin (Wu et al., 2019). However, the *bla*_{NDM} genes have also been commonly detected within other plasmid replicon types including IncFIA, IncFIB, IncFII and IncX3. The location of the *bla*_{NDM-5} gene has also recently been confirmed to reside within an IncFIB plasmid in an environmental isolate from natural waters in Switzerland (Bleichenbacher et al., 2020).

4.7. Sampling cold spots

A total of 6 cold spot locations were sampled twice throughout the longitudinal survey periods to evaluate the natural resistome in the absence of anthropogenic activity. This encompassed water bodies that were free from known discharges upstream or in close proximity to sample sites, and low to medium agricultural activity (Fig. 1). These sampling sites included estuary C and C1 in Fingal, river A and A1 in Galway City as well as beach J and lake D in Galway County. Extended-spectrum beta-lactamase-producing Enterobacterales were identified from the samples collected from Galway City and Fingal in line with the findings of the point prevalence survey. As discussed previously, estuary C received storm water overflow discharges in previous years and has a large wildlife presence (Hooban et al., 2021). Estuary C1 was located just 1.3 km from estuary C. River A is located at the boundary, upstream of Galway City. However, many houses, boats and wildlife reside in the area. Four isolates were selected for sequencing from river A (B19404), estuary C (B19678(a)) and estuary C1 (B19673, B20289) across both sampling periods. Isolate B19404 displayed a limited resistance gene profile with the detection of *bla*_{CTX-M-15} and efflux pump *mdf(A)*. In contrast, sequenced isolates from estuary C and C1 harbored *bla*_{CTX-M} in addition to sulphonamide (*sul2*), tetracycline (*tet(A)*), quinolone (*qnrS1*), aminoglycoside (*aph(3'')-Ib*, *aph(6)-Id*) and chloramphenicol (*floR*) resistance genes. This is potentially owing to the fact that previous storm water overflow discharges fed in to the water body. The remaining two cold spot locations within Galway County did not harbor any ESBL

producers. The location of these two sites were in more remote and less densely populated regions.

Comparison of the cold spot locations to the waters receiving anthropogenic discharges demonstrates the impact of anthropogenic activity on the dissemination of antibiotic resistance. The detection of carbapenem resistant and carbapenemase-producing isolates solely in 'hot spot' locations indicates that these resistance types in the environment may be primarily of human origin. Similarly, the two most remote regions (beach J and lake D) were void of ESBL detection in comparison to the areas with a larger human presence. Moreover, no Enterobacterales were isolated across either sample collection round for beach J indicative that the natural presence of Enterobacterales is less likely in uncontaminated seawater.

5. Conclusion

Information in relation to the aquatic environment as a reservoir and potential transmission route of antibiotic resistance is currently lacking, due to the absence of routine monitoring. To address this knowledge gap, this study investigated the natural resistome of different aquatic environments across Ireland on a longitudinal basis. The detection of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase and carbapenemase-producing Enterobacterales in waters across all seasons demonstrates the need for extended periods of bathing water monitoring, especially in countries where recreational water use is year round. A harmonised surveillance approach is necessary which encompasses screening for clinically significant, antibiotic resistance threats in order to adequately inform public health. Attempts to identify the sources of environmental antibiotic resistance were successful through cgMLST comparisons, which revealed identical isolates from different wastewaters and the surrounding waters. The influence of anthropogenic activity was further established through comparison of areas receiving multiple discharges to 'cold spot' locations. The overall body of evidence accumulated from this study suggests that anthropogenic discharges play a significant role in the dissemination of antibiotic resistance to the natural environment. Further work is needed to fully elucidate the potential health implications of ingestion of these resistant organisms through recreational exposure.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Brigid Hooban: Investigation, Formal analysis, Writing - original draft, Visualization.

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Louise O'Connor: Conceptualization, Investigation, Resources, Writing - review & editing.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supplementary data

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References

- Abid, F.B., Tsui, C.K.M., Doi, Y., Deshmukh, A., McElheny, C.L., Bachman, W.C., et al., 2021. Molecular characterization of clinical carbapenem-resistant Enterobacterales from Qatar. *Eur. J. Clin. Microbiol. Infect. Dis.* 40, 1779–1785.
- Allen, H.K., Donato, J., Wang, H.H., Cloud-Hansen, K.A., Davies, J., Handelsman, J., 2010. Call of the wild: antibiotic resistance genes in natural environments. *Nat. Rev. Microbiol.* 8, 251–259.
- Almakki, A., Jumas-Bilak, E., Marchandin, H., Licznar-Fajardo, P., 2019. Antibiotic resistance in urban runoff. *Sci. Total Environ.* 667, 64–76.
- Alsharapy, S.A., Gharout-Sait, A., Muggeo, A., Guillard, T., Cholley, P., Brasme, L., et al., 2020. Characterization of carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae clinical isolates in Al Thawra University Hospital, Sana'a, Yemen. *Microb. Drug Resist.* 26, 211–217.
- Bengtsson-Palme, J., Larsson, D.G.J., 2016. Concentrations of antibiotics predicted to select for resistant bacteria: proposed limits for environmental regulation. *Environ. Int.* 86, 140–149.
- Birkett, C.I., Ludlam, H.A., Woodford, N., Brown, D.F.J., Brown, N.M., Roberts, M.T.M., et al., 2007. Real-time TaqMan PCR for rapid detection and typing of genes encoding CTX-M extended-spectrum beta-lactamases. *J. Med. Microbiol.* 56, 52–55.
- Bitar, I., Piazza, A., Gaiarsa, S., Villa, L., Pedroni, P., Oliva, E., et al., 2017. ST405 NDM-5 producing *Escherichia coli* in Northern Italy: the first two clinical cases. *Clin. Microbiol. Infect.* 23, 489–490.
- Bleichenbacher, S., Stevens, M.J.A., Zurluh, K., Perreten, V., Endimiani, A., Stephan, R., et al., 2020. Environmental dissemination of carbapenemase-producing Enterobacteriaceae in rivers in Switzerland. *Environ. Pollut.* 265, 115081.
- Bolger, A.M., Lohse, M., Usadel, B., 2014. Trimmomatic: a flexible trimmer for Illumina sequence data. *Bioinformatics* 30, 2114–2120.
- Brehony, C., McGrath, E., Brennan, W., Tuohy, A., Whyte, T., Brisse, S., et al., 2019. An MLST approach to support tracking of plasmids carrying OXA-48-like carbapenemase. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* 74, 1856–1862.
- Cantón, R., Gonzalez-Alba, J.M., Galán, J.C., 2012. CTX-M enzymes: origin and diffusion. *Front. Microbiol.* 3, 110.
- Carattoli, A., Zankari, E., García-Fernández, A., Voldby Larsen, M., Lund, O., Villa, L., et al., 2014. In silico detection and typing of plasmids using PlasmidFinder and plasmid multilocus sequence typing. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 58, 3895–3903.
- Chique, C., Cullinan, J., Hooban, B., Morris, D., 2019. Mapping and analysing potential sources and transmission routes of antimicrobial resistant organisms in the environment using geographic information systems—an exploratory study. *Antibiotics* 8, 16.
- de Lima Procópio, R.E., da Silva, I.R., Martins, M.K., de Azevedo, J.L., de Araújo, J.M., 2012. Antibiotics produced by streptomycetes. *Braz. J. Infect. Dis.* 16, 466–471.
- Department of Health, 2017. Ireland's National Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance 2017–2020. Available at <http://health.gov.ie/national-patient-safety-office/patient-safety-surveillance/antimicrobial-resistance-amr>.
- Dortet, L., Nordmann, P., Poirel, L., 2012. Association of the emerging carbapenemase NDM-1 with a bleomycin resistance protein in Enterobacteriaceae and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 56, 1693–1697.
- Eramo, A., Delos Reyes, H., Fahrenfeld, N.L., 2017. Partitioning of antibiotic resistance genes and fecal indicators varies intra and inter-storm during combined sewer overflows. *Front. Microbiol.* 8, 2024.
- EUCAST, 2021. European Committee on Antimicrobial Susceptibility Testing Breakpoint tables for Interpretation of MICs and Zone Diameters. Version 11.0, valid from 2021-01-01 https://www.eucast.org/fileadmin/src/media/PDFs/EUCAST_files/Breakpoint_tables/v_11.0_Breakpoint_Tables.pdf.
- European Centre for Disease Prevention and Control, 2019. Carbapenem-resistant Enterobacteriaceae, Second Update – 26 September 2019. ECDC, Stockholm Available at <https://www.ecdc.europa.eu/sites/default/files/documents/carbapenem-resistant-enterobacteriaceae-risk-assessment-rev-2.pdf> (Accessed 22nd July 2021).
- European Food Safety Authority, 2018. Scientific Opinion on Chloramphenicol in Food and Feed Available at <https://efsa.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/pdf/10.2903/j.efsa.2014.3907>. (Accessed 20th July 2021).
- Farrell, M.L., Joyce, A., Duane, S., Fitzhenry, K., Hooban, B., Burke, L.P., et al., 2021. Evaluating the potential for exposure to organisms of public health concern in naturally occurring bathing waters in Europe: a scoping review. *Water Res.* 206, 117711.
- Gong, X., Zhang, J., Su, S., Fu, Y., Bao, M., Wang, Y., et al., 2018. Molecular characterization and epidemiology of carbapenem non-susceptible Enterobacteriaceae isolated from the Eastern region of Heilongjiang Province, China. *BMC Infect. Dis.* 18, 417.

- Corrie, C.L., Mirceta, M., Wick, R.R., Judd, L.M., Wyres, K.L., Thomson, N.R., et al., 2018. Antimicrobial-resistant *Klebsiella pneumoniae* carriage and infection in specialized geriatric care wards linked to acquisition in the referring hospital. *Clin. Infect. Dis. Off. Publ. Infect. Dis. Soc. Am.* 67, 161–170.
- Gupta, S.K., Padmanabhan, B.R., Diene, S.M., Lopez-Rojas, R., Kempf, M., Landraud, L., et al., 2014. ARG-ANNOT, a new bioinformatic tool to discover antibiotic resistance genes in bacterial genomes. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 58, 212–220.
- Hamprecht, A., Sommer, J., Willmann, M., Brender, C., Stelzer, Y., Krause, F.F., et al., 2019. Pathogenicity of clinical OXA-48 isolates and impact of the OXA-48 IncI plasmid on virulence and bacterial fitness. *Front. Microbiol.* 10, 2509.
- He, Y., Yuan, Q., Mathieu, J., Stadler, L., Senehi, N., Sun, R., et al., 2020. Antibiotic resistance genes from livestock waste: occurrence, dissemination, and treatment. *npj Clean Water* 3, 4.
- Health Products Regulatory Authority, 2019. Report on sales of veterinary antibiotics in Ireland during 2019. Available at <https://www.hpra.ie/docs/default-source/publications-forms/newsletters/report-on-sales-of-veterinary-antibiotics-in-ireland-during-2019.pdf?sfvrsn=11> (Accessed 20th July 2021).
- Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2019. Enhanced Surveillance of Carbapenemase-Producing Enterobacteriales (CPE), 2018. Available at <https://www.hpsc.ie/a-z/microbiologyantimicrobialresistance/strategyforthecontrolofantimicrobialresistanceinirelandsari/carbapenemresistantenterobacteriaceae/surveillanceofcpeinireland/cpeannualreports/CPE%20Enhanced%20Surveillance%20Report%202018.pdf> (Accessed 21st July 2021).
- Health Protection Surveillance Centre, 2020. Hospital Antimicrobial Consumption Surveillance. Available at <https://www.hpsc.ie/a-z/microbiologyantimicrobialresistance/europeansurveillanceofantimicrobialconsumptionesac/PublicMicroB/SACHC/Report1.html> (Accessed 6th July 2021).
- Hernando-Amado, S., Coque, T.M., Baquero, F., Martínez, J.L., 2019. Defining and combating antibiotic resistance from One Health and Global Health perspectives. *Nat. Microbiol.* 4, 1432–1442.
- Hooban, B., Joyce, A., Fitzhenry, K., Chique, C., Morris, D., 2020. The role of the natural aquatic environment in the dissemination of extended spectrum beta-lactamase and carbapenemase encoding genes: a scoping review. *Water Res.* 180, 115880.
- Hooban, B., Fitzhenry, K., Cahill, N., Joyce, A., O'Connor, L., Bray, J.E., et al., 2021. A point prevalence survey of antibiotic resistance in the Irish environment, 2018–2019. *Environ. Int.* 152, 106466.
- Hu, Y.-Y., Cai, J.-C., Zhou, H.-W., Chi, D., Zhang, X.-F., Chen, W.-L., et al., 2013. Molecular typing of CTX-M-producing *Escherichia coli* isolates from environmental water, swine feces, specimens from healthy humans, and human patients. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 79, 5988–5996.
- Jolley, K.A., Bray, J.E., MCJ, Maiden, 2018. Open-access bacterial population genomics: BIGSdb software, the PubMLST.org website and their applications. *Wellcome Open Research* 3, 124 (2018); 3).
- Khan, E.R., Aung, M.S., Paul, S.K., Ahmed, S., Haque, N., Ahamed, F., et al., 2018. Prevalence and molecular epidemiology of clinical isolates of *Escherichia coli* and *Klebsiella pneumoniae* harboring extended-spectrum beta-lactamase and carbapenemase genes in Bangladesh. *Microb. Drug Resist.* 24, 1568–1579.
- Kim, J.Y., Lee, H., Lee, J.E., Chung, M.-S., Ko, G.P., 2013. Identification of human and animal fecal contamination after rainfall in the Han River, Korea. *Microbes Environ.* 28, 187–194.
- Kumar, M., Jaiswal, S., Sodhi, K.K., Shree, P., Singh, D.K., Agrawal, P.K., et al., 2019. Antibiotics bioremediation: perspectives on its ecotoxicity and resistance. *Environ. Int.* 124, 448–461.
- Lee, I., Chalita, M., Ha, S.M., Na, S.I., Yoon, S.H., Chun, J., 2017. ContEst16S: an algorithm that identifies contaminated prokaryotic genomes using 16S RNA gene sequences. *Int. J. Syst. Evol. Microbiol.* 67, 2053–2057.
- Leonard, A.F.C., Zhang, L., Balfour, A.J., Garside, R., Hawkey, P.M., Murray, A.K., et al., 2018. Exposure to and colonisation by antibiotic-resistant *E. coli* in UK coastal water users: environmental surveillance, exposure assessment, and epidemiological study (Beach Bum Survey). *Environ. Int.* 114, 326–333.
- Lu, J., Zhang, J., Xu, L., Liu, Y., Li, P., Zhu, T., et al., 2018. Spread of the florfenicol resistance floR gene among clinical *Klebsiella pneumoniae* isolates in China. *Antimicrob. Resist. Infect. Control* 7, 127.
- Lyu, Q., Bai, K., Kan, Y., Jiang, N., Thapa, S.P., Coaker, G., et al., 2019. Variation in streptomycin resistance mechanisms in *Clavibacter michiganensis*. *Phytopathology*® 109, 1849–1858.
- Manchanda, V., Rai, S., Gupta, S., Rautela, R.S., Chopra, R., Rawat, D.S., et al., 2011. Development of TaqMan real-time polymerase chain reaction for the detection of the newly emerging form of carbapenem resistance gene in clinical isolates of *Escherichia coli*, *Klebsiella pneumoniae*, and *Acinetobacter baumannii*. *Indian J. Med. Microbiol.* 29, 249–253.
- Markovska, R., Stankova, P., Stoeva, T., Ivanova, D., Pencheva, D., Kaneva, R., et al., 2021. Fecal carriage and epidemiology of extended-spectrum beta-lactamase/carbapenemases producing Enterobacteriales isolates in Bulgarian hospitals. *Antibiotics (Basel, Switzerland)* 10, 747.
- McArthur, A.G., Waglechner, N., Nizam, F., Yan, A., Azad, M.A., Baylay, A.J., et al., 2013. The comprehensive antibiotic resistance database. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 57, 3348–3357.
- Monahan, C., Nag, R., Morris, D., Cummins, E., 2021. Antibiotic residues in the aquatic environment - current perspective and risk considerations. *J. Environ. Sci. Health A Tox. Hazard. Subst. Environ. Eng.* 1–19.
- Mori, T., Mizuta, S., Suenaga, H., Miyazaki, K., 2008. Metagenomic screening for bleomycin resistance genes. *Appl. Environ. Microbiol.* 74, 6803–6805.
- Morris, D., Kavanagh, S., Carney, K., MacDomhnaill, B., Cormican, M., 2016. CapE (capture, amplify, extract): a rapid method for detection of low level contamination of water with Verocytotoxigenic *Escherichia coli* (VTEC). *Sci. Total Environ.* 563–564, 267–272.
- Muller, A., Gbaguidi-Haore, H., Cholley, P., Hocquet, D., Sauget, M., Bertrand, X., 2021. Hospital-diagnosed infections with *Escherichia coli* clonal group ST131 are mostly acquired in the community. *Sci. Rep.* 11, 5702.
- Nakamura-Silva, R., Oliveira-Silva, M., Furlan, J.P.R., Stehling, E.G., Miranda, C.E.S., Pitondo-Silva, A., 2021. Characterization of multidrug-resistant and virulent *Klebsiella pneumoniae* strains belonging to the high-risk clonal group 258 (CG258) isolated from inpatients in northeastern Brazil. *Arch. Microbiol.* 203, 4351–4359.
- Official Journal of the European Union, d. Directive 2006/7/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council. Available at <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/PDF/?uri=CELEX:32006L0007&from=EN> (Accessed 20th July 2021).
- O'Flaherty, E., Solimini, A., Pantanella, F., Cummins, E., 2019. The potential human exposure to antibiotic resistant-*Escherichia coli* through recreational water. *Sci. Total Environ.* 650, 786–795.
- Paramita, R.I., Nelwan, E.J., Fadilah, F., Renestee, E., Puspadari, N., Erlina, L., 2020. Genome-based characterization of *Escherichia coli* causing bloodstream infection through next-generation sequencing. *PLoS One* 15, e0244358.
- Partridge, S.R., Kwong, S.M., Firth, N., Jensen, S.O., 2018. Mobile genetic elements associated with antimicrobial resistance. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.* 31, e00088-17.
- Pazda, M., Kumirska, J., Stepnowski, P., Mulkiewicz, E., 2019. Antibiotic resistance genes identified in wastewater treatment plant systems – a review. *Sci. Total Environ.* 697, 134023.
- Prijbelski, A., Antipov, D., Meleshko, D., Lapidus, A., Korobeynikov, A., 2020. Using SPAdes De Novo Assembler. *Curr. Protoc. Bioinformatics* 70, e102.
- Quijada, N.M., Rodríguez-Lázaro, D., Eiros, J.M., Hernández, M., 2019. TORMES: an automated pipeline for whole bacterial genome analysis. *Bioinformatics* 35, 4207–4212.
- Ranjana, A., Shaik, S., Mondal, A., Nandanwar, N., Hussain, A., Semmler, T., et al., 2016. Molecular epidemiology and genome dynamics of New Delhi Metallo-β-lactamase-producing extraintestinal pathogenic *Escherichia coli* strains from India. *Antimicrob. Agents Chemother.* 60, 6795–6805.
- Reygaert, W.C., 2018. An overview of the antimicrobial resistance mechanisms of bacteria. *AIMS Microbiol.* 4, 482–501.
- Rodriguez-Mozaz, S., Vaz-Moreira, I., Varela Della Giustina, S., Llorca, M., Barceló, D., Schubert, S., et al., 2020. Antibiotic residues in final effluents of European wastewater treatment plants and their impact on the aquatic environment. *Environ. Int.* 140, 105733.
- Sampson, R.W., Swiatnicki, S.A., McDermott, C.M., Kleinheinz, G.T., 2006. The effects of rainfall on *Escherichia coli* and total coliform levels at 15 lake superior recreational beaches. *Water Resour. Manag.* 20, 151–159.
- Schwarz, S., Kehrenberg, C., Doublet, B., Cloeckaert, A., 2004. Molecular basis of bacterial resistance to chloramphenicol and florfenicol. *FEMS Microbiol. Rev.* 28, 519–542.
- Shen, B., Du, L., Sanchez, C., Edwards, D.J., Chen, M., Murrell, J.M., 2002. Cloning and characterization of the bleomycin biosynthetic gene cluster from *Streptomyces verticillus* ATCC15003. *J. Nat. Prod.* 65, 422–431.
- Sommer, J., Gerbracht, K.M., Krause, F.F., Wild, F., Tietgen, M., Riedel-Christ, S., et al., 2021. OXA-484, an OXA-48-type carbapenem-hydrolyzing class D β-lactamase from *Escherichia coli*. *Front. Microbiol.* 12, 1100.
- Swayne, R.L., Ludlam, H.A., Shet, V.G., Woodford, N., Curran, M.D., 2011. Real-time TaqMan PCR for rapid detection of genes encoding five types of non-metallo- (class A and D) carbapenemases in Enterobacteriaceae. *Int. J. Antimicrob. Agents* 38, 35–58.
- Takayama, Y., Sekizuka, T., Matsui, H., Adachi, Y., Eda, R., Nihonyanagi, S., et al., 2020. Characterization of the IncFII-IncFIB(pB171) plasmid carrying blaNDM-5 in *Escherichia coli* ST405 clinical isolate in Japan. *Infect. Drug Resist.* 13, 561–566.
- Umezawa, H., Maeda, K., Takeuchi, T., Okami, Y., 1966. New antibiotics, bleomycin A and B. *J. Antibiotics* 19, 200–209.
- Ventola, C.L., 2015. The antibiotic resistance crisis: part 1: causes and threats. *P & T Peer-reviewed J. Formul. Manag.* 40, 277–283.
- Whitmer, G.R., Moorthy, G., Arshad, M., 2019. The pandemic *Escherichia coli* sequence type 131 strain is acquired even in the absence of antibiotic exposure. *PLoS Pathog.* 15, e1008162.
- Wood, D.E., Salzberg, S.L., 2014. Kraken: ultrafast metagenomic sequence classification using exact alignments. *Genome Biol.* 15, R46.
- World Health Organization, 2015. Global Action Plan on Antimicrobial Resistance. Available at https://apps.who.int/iris/bitstream/handle/10665/193736/9789241509763_eng.pdf?sequence=1 (Accessed 27th July 2021).
- World Health Organization, 2017. Global Priority List of Antibiotic-Resistant Bacteria to Guide Research, Discovery, and Development of New Antibiotics. Available at https://www.who.int/medicines/publications/WHO-PPL-Short_Summary_25Feb-ET_NM_WHO.pdf (Accessed 26th July 2021).
- Wu, W., Feng, Y., Tang, G., Qiao, F., McNally, A., Zong, Z., 2019. NDM metallo-β-lactamases and their bacterial producers in health care settings. *Clin. Microbiol. Rev.* 32.
- Wyer, M.D., Kay, D., Morgan, H., Naylor, S., Clark, S., Watkins, J., et al., 2018. Within-day variability in microbial concentrations at a UK designated bathing water: implications for regulatory monitoring and the application of predictive modelling based on historical compliance data. *Water Res.* X 1, 100006.
- Zankari, E., Hasman, H., Cosentino, S., Vestergaard, M., Rasmussen, S., Lund, O., et al., 2012. Identification of acquired antimicrobial resistance genes. *J. Antimicrob. Chemother.* 67, 2640–2644.
- Zhang, A.-N., Gaston, J.M., Dai, C.L., Zhao, S., Poyet, M., Groussin, M., et al., 2021. An omics-based framework for assessing the health risk of antimicrobial resistance genes. *Nat. Commun.* 12, 4765.
- Zhou, Z., Alikhan, N.-F., Sergeant, M.J., Luhmann, N., Vaz, C., Francisco, A.P., et al., 2018. GrapeTree: visualization of core genomic relationships among 100,000 bacterial pathogens. *Genome Res.* 28, 1395–1404.